

Numerical Modelling Study of Subaqueous Dune Saturation

A. Doré¹, G. Coco¹

¹ School of Environment, University of Auckland, Auckland, New Zealand. arnaud.dore@auckland.ac.nz

1. Introduction

Observations of bedform development show that an initially flatbed evolves through different phases: an incipient bedform phase, a growing phase and a stabilizing phase leading to a fully developed dune field. For non-suspended transport in the limit of a large flow thickness, Duran et al. (2019) showed that Re_d^* encodes the hydrodynamic roughness and controls the appearance of a hydrodynamic anomaly leading to ripple saturation. Dune saturation in finite flow depth, on the other hand, is still an open problem. Physical mechanisms induced by the presence of the free surface and suspended sediment transport seem to be related to dune saturation (Charru, 2013 ; Naqshband et al., 2014b). In the present work we use a 2D RANS model (Doré et al., 2016) to simulate dune profiles at different stages of their evolution, compute the value of the phase deviation of the maximum of the bed shear stress, $\delta_{\varphi,tb}$, and sediment fluxes, $\delta_{\varphi,qb}$ (bedload), $\delta_{\varphi,qS}$ (suspension) and $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ (total). Results agree with experimental data and a previous numerical modelling study. A parametric study on the main non-dimensional parameters controlling the system provides a deeper insight into the process of saturation in finite flow depth.

2. Numerical model and Methods

The model solves the Reynolds Averaged Navier Stokes equations in the boundary layer. The sediment transport module calculates the bedload flux using the formulation of Meyer-Peter and Müller (1948), and the suspended sediment concentration is calculated through an advection-diffusion equation. For a detailed description of the model, see Doré et al. (2016). Applying steady forcing conditions, we compute the bedform morphological evolution for fixed values of the adimensional depth, $kD = 2\pi D/\lambda$. After a certain time interval, that depends on the initial profile shape and applied conditions, the phase lag eventually stabilizes and the wavelength is locked due to the streamwise confinement. Values of $\delta_{\varphi,tb}$, $\delta_{\varphi,qb}$, $\delta_{\varphi,qS}$ and $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ are computed and their variation is analysed.

3. Results

The approach is tested by comparing with the experimental scenario of Naqshband et al. (2014a). The model parametrization is like Dore et al. (2016). Figure 1 shows the evolution of the computed values of $\delta_{\varphi,qb}$, $\delta_{\varphi,qS}$ and $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ as function of kD . $\delta_{\varphi,qb}$, is always positive within the investigated range of values, whereas $\delta_{\varphi,qS}$ and $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ exhibit a sharp dip for $kD < 0.8$. The curve of $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ crosses the abscissa axis for $kD = 0.67$ which is remarkably close to the experimental value of $kD = 0.69$.

Figure 1. Evolution of $\delta_{\varphi,qb}$, $\delta_{\varphi,qS}$ and $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ versus kD .

The parametric study revealed the influence of KD , θ and L_{sat} on dune saturation. As dunes grow, their profiles perturb the flow over a vertical distance proportional to their wavelength, constrained by the water depth (KD). Turbulence relaxation downstream of the crests further increase the Reynolds stresses in the outer layer (θ). As a result, fluid inertia decreases, reducing the phase advance. As $\delta_{\varphi,tb}$ is getting lower and the turbulent kinetic energy increases, larger quantities of suspended sediment are carried downstream of the crest, modulated by L_{sat} . Saturation is achieved as $\delta_{\varphi,qT}$ becomes null, depending on $\delta_{\varphi,qb}$, $\delta_{\varphi,qS}$, and the relative weight of the sediment fluxes.

Acknowledgments

Supported by H2020-MSCA-IF-2020 grant No.101021848.

References

- Charru, F. (2013). Sand ripples and dunes, *Annual Review of Fluid Mechanics*, 45, 469-493.
- Coleman, S. E., and B. W. Melville, *Journal of Hydraulic Engineering- ASCE*, 120, 544-560, (1994).
- Doré A., P. Bonneton P., V. Marieu, T. Garlan, (2016). Numerical modeling of subaqueous sand dunes morphodynamics, *Journal of geophysical research : earth surface*, doi: 10.1002/2015JF003689.
- Duran Vinent, O., Andreotti, B., et al. (2019). A unified model of ripples and dunes in water and planetary environments. *Nat. Geosci.* **12**, 345–350, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41561-019-0336-4>.
- Kennedy, J. F., (1963). The mechanics of dunes and antidunes in erodible-bed channels, *Journal of Fluid Mechanics*, 16, 521-544.
- Naqshband, S., J. Ribberink, et al. (2014a). Bed load and suspended load contributions to migrating sand dunes in equilibrium, *Journal of Geophysical Research*, 119, 1043-1063, doi :10.1002/2013JF003043.